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Family	Name	Gene ID in database	Gene length (bp)	ORF length (bp)	Protein length (aa)
PYL1 like	PYL1a	NbD001180	678	678	225
PYL1 like	PYL1b	NbD012105	678	678	225
PYL8/9 like	PYL8a	NbD015117	1944	528	175
PYL8/9 like	PYL8b	NbD008843	2020	528	175
PYL8/9 like	PYL8c	NbD004872	3126	558	185
PYL4/5 like	PYL4b	NbD014593	642	642	213
PYL4/5 like	PYL4d	NbE03056248	636	636	212

Figure S1. Target gene sequences and deduced protein size of the gene products. **(A)** Genomic structure of the 7 ABA receptor genes targeted in this study, indicating the gRNAs corresponding to each gene. **(B)** Nomenclature of the genes according to www.nbent.com database. Gene identity (ID), open reading frame (ORF) length from ATG to stop codon and protein length are indicated.